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Recommendations on Vibration-Based Method application to Structural Health Monitoring of Low and Medium-rise Buildings under Ambient Vibrations

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Foreword

Developments of practical guidelines always enhance the effective transfer of achievements of theoretical studies and the engineering applications to practice and forms a framework of standards for industry applications. A standard is a useful method of distributing and putting into practice research's findings. These guidelines complement the list of guidelines given in the *Annex* by providing both general recommendations and specific recommendations for monitoring low- and medium-rise buildings. These recommendations for monitoring of low and medium rise buildings originates from investigations performed during 2020 – 2022 under the project “*Structural Health Monitoring of Buildings under Ambient Vibrations*”.

Medium and low-rise buildings characterise with a relatively predictable global modes of vibration, but identification difficulties can cause closely spaced modes and noisy measurements due to very low ambient vibration amplitudes. As well as such buildings has a certain range of natural frequencies, the significant influence of the stiffness of the supports on the global modal parameters, low global stiffness reduction due to local damage, the influence of operational and environmental conditions on modal parameters, and practically unidentifiable damping characteristics from the ambient vibrations.

Although the structure of these guidelines is like the European standards for the construction industry, references are included throughout the text to make it easy for readers to find additional information. Definitions and explanations of terms used in the following are given at the beginning of the document.

1. Section 1 General

1.1. Scope

These guidelines intended to provide some recommendations for testing and monitoring of low- and medium-rise buildings under ambient vibration condition (no strong motion). Users need to interpret the guidance given in this document flexibly and could use it as a starting point to navigate through the scattered information across several engineering disciplines.

1.2. Terms and definitions

A basic list of terms and definitions given in document mostly based on terms defined in ISO 2041:2018(en) “Mechanical vibration, shock and condition monitoring — Vocabulary”, ISO 18431-1:2005(en) “Mechanical vibration and shock — Signal processing — Part 1: General introduction” and SAMCO guidelines¹. Reference given separately if the definition is taken from elsewhere. Definitions are given in alphabetic order.

Accelerometer

Acceleration transducer - transducer that converts an input acceleration to an output (usually electrical) that is proportional to the input acceleration.

Ambient vibration - all-encompassing vibration associated with a given environment usually a composite vibration from many surrounding sources.

Ambient vibration measurements – vibration behaviour of a structure is recorded, evaluated and interpreted under ambient influences, i.e., without artificial excitation, by means of highly sensitive sensors [6].

Broad-band random vibration

Broad-band stochastic vibration - random vibration having its frequency components distributed over a broad frequency band.

Coupled modes - modes of vibration that influence one another because of energy transfer from one mode to another through damping. An energy transfer results from the neighbouring natural frequencies.

¹ “SAMCO NETWORK.”, <http://www.samco.org/>. Accessed 13 Aug. 2022.

Damage - intentional or unintentional changes to the material and/or geometric properties of these systems, including changes to the boundary conditions and system connectivity, which adversely affect the current or future performance of these systems [2].

Data Acquisition System (DAS) – onsite system where signal demodulation, conditioning and storage of measured data are conducted prior to being transferred to an offsite location for analysis (the datalogger). For most sensors an input signal is required, and then interpretation of the sensor output signal must be conducted to convert the analogue sensor response into engineering terms.

Damage feature - damage-sensitive quantity or parameter that can be related to the health state of the structure [3].

Data normalisation - process of separating changes in the features derived from sensor readings that are caused by damage from those changes caused by EOVs [2].

Electromechanical transducer (sensor in this guide) – transducer that is actuated by energy from a mechanical system (strain, force, motion, etc.), and supplies energy to an electrical system, or vice versa.

FDD - Frequency Domain Decomposition that is based on the singular value decomposition (SVD) of the spectral density matrix [4].

Fixed-base natural frequency - natural frequency that a system would have if the foundation to which the equipment is attached is rigid and of infinite mass.

Fundamental natural mode of vibration - mode of vibration of a system having the lowest natural frequency.

Frequency-response function (FRF) – the frequency-dependent ratio of the motion-response Fourier transform to the Fourier transform of the excitation force of a linear system.

Input – output method – direct measurements of the varying environmental or operational parameters are available therefore various types of regression and interpolation analyses can be performed to relate measurements relevant to structural damage and those associated with environmental and operation variation of the system [8].

Low and medium-rise building – in this guide Low-rise buildings are defined as buildings with 3 floors or under. Medium-rise buildings are defined as buildings between 4 to 12 floors.

Modal analysis - vibration analysis method that characterizes a complicated, linear system by its modes of vibration, i.e., natural frequencies, modal damping, and mode shapes.

Machine learning (ML) – the use and development of computer systems that are able to learn and adapt without following explicit instructions, by using algorithms and statistical models to analyse and draw inferences from patterns in data [7].

Noise - undesired signal, generally of a random nature, the spectrum of which does not exhibit clearly defined frequency components.

Nyquist frequency - maximum usable frequency available in data taken at a given sampling rate

The Nyquist frequency is $f_N = f_s/2$, where f_s is the sampling frequency.

Natural mode of vibration - mode of vibration assumed by a system when vibrating freely at a natural frequency.

Operational and Environmental Variability (EOV) – changing environmental and operational conditions that affect measured signals, and these ambient variations of the system can often mask subtle changes in the system's vibration signal caused by damage [8].

Operational Modal Analysis (OMA) – an engineering field that studies the modal properties of systems under ambient vibrations or normal operating conditions [5].

Output-only method for data normalization – method to distinguish changes caused by damage from those caused by the operational and environmental variation of the system without measuring the operational and environmental parameters [8].

Rocking frequency – frequency of the building vibrating as a whole block in rocking motion

RMS - root-mean-square value.

Random vibration

Stochastic vibration - vibration where the instantaneous value cannot be predicted.

Sampling - measurement of a varying physical quantity at a sequence of values of time, angle, revolutions, or other mechanical, independent variable.

Signal bandwidth - interval over frequency between the upper and lower frequencies of interest.

Sway (unbraced) frame - the frames that provide lateral resistance mainly through columns are considered to be sway frames (unbraced) [9].

Sampling frequency

Sampling rate - number of samples with respect to time, angle, revolutions or other mechanical, independent variable for uniformly sampled data.

Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) –a non-destructive in-situ structural evaluation method that uses any of several types of sensors which are attached to, or embedded in, a structure. These sensors obtain various types of data (either continuously or periodically), which are then collected, analysed and stored for future analysis and reference. The data can be used to assess the safety, integrity, strength, or performance of the structure, and to identify damage at its onset.

SSI effect - soil-structure interaction is a physical phenomenon in which the structure fails to behave independently and behaves in connection with the soil when an external load is applied to the structure.

Singular value decomposition (SVD) - Singular value decomposition (SVD) is a method of representing a matrix as a series of linear approximations that expose the underlying meaning-structure of the matrix

Time history - sequence of values of a physical or engineering quantity as a function of time.

Vibration Based Methods (VBM) – the use of in situ non-destructive sensing and analysis of system characteristics – in the time, frequency, or modal domains – for the purpose of detecting changes, which may indicate damage or degradation [1].

Vibration Monitoring System (VMS) - a complete system that is capable of acquiring vibration signals according to pre-determined parameters such as sampling frequency, vibration level, recording length, recording intervals and frequency bandwidths. The system should be able to process the recorded vibration and translate the information into engineering terms.

White random vibration

White stochastic vibration - vibration that has equal energy for any frequency band of constant width over the spectrum of interest.

1.3. Symbols

SN - Signal-to-noise ratio;

f – fundamental frequency of building

f_{max} – maximum structural frequency of interest during the monitoring campaign;

f_{min} – minimum structural frequency of interest during the monitoring campaign;

f_r – rocking frequency;

f_s – sampling frequency;

f_{st} – fundamental frequency for the fixed base model of building;

y_{max} – maximum instantaneous value of the signal that can be transmitted by the system without distortion;

σ_n – RMS value of background noise;

∂t – synchronization error of data between different sensors.

2. Section 2 SHM – VBM Principal Scheme

2.1. General considerations

The automatic and permanent monitoring of structure aims to improve knowledge of the current state and long-term behaviour including influences. The goal of SHM system is to identify and quantify any damage or deterioration state that might occur over the service life of building [10].

Damage identification based upon changes in vibration characteristics is one of the few methods that monitor changes in the structure on a global basis [11] therefore called **global method**. This method uses the lower vibration modes of structure for the extraction of damage sensitive features. There are four levels on the damage assessment scale that is generally accepted [12]:

- 1) Level 1: Damage detection (provides information that damage is present in the structure);
- 2) Level 2: Damage localization (determining the location(s) of single or multiple damage places);
- 3) Level 3: Damage quantification (the extent of damage is evaluated e.g. extent of damage evaluated);
- 4) Level 4: The prognosis of the remaining lifetime.

Principal components of ambient VBM method shown in Figure 1. The ability to convert sensor data into SHM information is directly related to the coupling of the sensor system hardware development with the data interrogation procedures [13].

Figure 1. Principal components of ambient VBM method

Main advantages of the VBM methods [14] are:

- No need for closely - spaced sensors and limited number of sensors even for large and complex structures;
- No need for prior information about expected location of damage in advance;
- Portable instruments for the SHM-VBM system.

The second axiom of SHM [15] states: “*The assessment of damage requires a comparison between two system states.*” For the reason that damage feature extraction process is based on fitting either **physics-based** or **data-based model** (derived from reference model or state) to the measured system response data. The parameters of these models or the predictive errors associated with these models are a damage sensitive features [13].

VBM Global methods can also be subdivided in **parametric methods** and **nonparametric methods** [16]. Parametric methods further subdivide in ML - based methods and Other methods which in turn can be **Input – output method** or **Output only methods**.

In parametric methods, vibration signals are acquired by the sensing system to monitor the physical properties (modal frequencies, modal mass, modal damping, stiffness or mode shapes) of the structure. Nonparametric methods utilize statistical means to detect structural damage directly from the measured accelerations, velocity, displacements, or dynamic strains.

2.2. General recommendations for low and medium-rise buildings

Recommendations stated in this chapter in more detailed explained in the next section of this guide.

- Only automatic and permanent monitoring with a sophisticated damage detection algorithms can bring valuable additional information about the overall stiffness changes in the building or its base. Short term VBM monitoring will be a “snapshot” of parameters polluted with the EOV condition. Nevertheless, short term VBM monitoring can be utilised together with vibration thresholds in cases of prognosed dynamic loading amplification, for example, due to construction works nearby. But this is out of the guide’s scope.
- Damage sensitivity is dependent on the building’s structural scheme including boundary conditions and as well as the extent and location. Generally, structural change like a failure of a single component will not cause a global effect and will not be detectable with this global VBM method.
- Output – only parameter identification methods and parametric damage identification methods are recommended for conducting automatic and permanent monitoring of building due to the expected noise signals and low amplitudes.
- Long-term monitoring data from the permanently installed monitoring system could form a base for the quantitative comparison of the structural health of buildings amongst each other. As well as the data could be reused when the theoretical evaluation is developed further due to the data’s long-lasting nature.

3. Section 3 Typical modal parameters

In the planning stage of VBM system development it is important to know the approximate dynamic parameters of the object to correctly select measurement technology described in the next section of this document. As well as it is important to assess the feasibility and value of information that can be extracted from monitoring campaign.

In case of low and medium rise buildings experimental data clearly show that use of the linear relationship between building height and fundamental frequency is not appropriate. The main parameters influencing the fundamental frequency of such buildings are geometry and material of building; soil underneath the building; type of foundation; presence of building frame "infills" or shear walls.

Highest scatter of the fundamental frequencies is for buildings of up to three floors due to considerable variations in their geometries and dependency on SSI effect. Typically, fundamental frequencies lie in the following ranges [17]:

Number of storeys of the building	Typical fundamental frequency range, Hz
1 – 3	1.2 - 12.5
4 – 5	0.7 - 6.5
6 – 7	0.8 - 4.8
8 – 9	0.7 - 3.3
10 – 12	0.7 - 3.5
13 – 16	0.4 - 2.2

Case studies show - buildings with a plan dimension close to the square have closely spaced first lateral and longitudinal mode shapes as expected. Still, buildings with rectangular plan dimensions could have closely spaced first longitudinal and first torsional mode shape. Torsional mode shapes from each other are usually well separated.

The damping is not discussed as it cannot be correctly identified for this type of buildings from ambient vibration records.

4. Section 4 Measurement Technology

The **Vibration Monitoring System** shall be furnished **on a system basis** because the complete measurement system defines the quality of the measured data not the individual elements themselves. This includes sensors with low noise flexible cables in flexible conduit or wireless system, necessary pre-amplifier/electronics mounted in local weatherproof boxes, mounting racks and cabinets etc, GUI software. The vibration monitoring system shall include all power supplies, interconnecting cabling, indicators, integrating units, signal conditioning devices, and all other accessories, for monitoring of vibration at each specified point and stability to the environmental conditions on-site.

An **analog antialiasing filter** must always be applied between the sensor and the DAS in order to effectively remove the energy of the signal outside of the Nyquist band [4]. It is recommended to use DAS with **sigma - delta technology** that samples at the maximum rate of $f_{s0} = 50\text{kHz}$ followed by subsequent decimation to the user defined sampling frequency f_s . **Signals should be sampled simultaneously**. Requirements for VBM settings and parameters as well as typical values for low and medium-rise buildings are set in the Tab. 1. Calculated values in Tab. 1. are only indicative for choosing the VBM system and should be calculated based on the actual situation.

For **low-rise buildings geophone sensors** are preferred due to the following advantages: sensor measures velocity, therefore displacement and acceleration can be obtained by differentiating or integrating signal only once, it has excellent noise properties and is cost-effective. The limitation is that **the linear frequency range** is limited to frequencies above the natural frequency of the sensor, which is typically around 4–12 Hz. But low rise building fundamental frequency mostly satisfies this requirement. Generally, the choice of the sensors depends on expected vibration levels on site. This is acceptable as a signal-to-noise ratio in the OMA. Therefore, the site microtremor level can be taken as the sensor noise floor requirement [4].

For calibrated sensors (absolute calibration is obligatory) relative calibration (collocation test) also should be performed prior to the beginning of the monitoring campaign according to the methodology given in [4]: place all sensors in “the same” location (as close as possible); take a simultaneous time record of all sensors; decimate the signal to include only the lowest modes of

the structure; calculate the RMS value from each signal; use the ratio between the RMS values as an indicator for relative calibration.

Number of measurement channels (1D sensors) should be larger than the physical rank of spectrum density matrix i.e. that is the maximum number of modes that are contributing to the response in chosen frequency band. Additionally, should be considered redundant channel in case the one of the sensors fails during the exploitation. Therefore, absolute minimum is 4 sensors for each thermal block of the building. Two of the reference sensors must be placed at the top corner of the building because it is never a node point for regular building structures. [4].

Requirements for VBM settings and parameters

Tab. 1

#	Parameter	Equation ²	Indicative values for low and mid-rise buildings ³
1.	Signal-to-noise ratio SN of time series	$SN = 20 \log \left(\frac{y_{max}}{\sigma_n} \right)$	$SN < 40$ dB
2.	Measurement duration for one data set according to ANSI S2.47	$T = \frac{200}{\xi f_{min}}$	Low rise: 0.5h ... 1.3h* Mid-rise: (4-5 floors) 0.9h ... 1.7h* (6-7 floors) 1.2h ... 2.2h* (8-9 floors) 1.6h ... 2.9h* (10-12 floors) 1.7h ... 3.3h*
3.	Maximum allowed data synchronization error ∂t	$\partial t = \frac{1}{(360 f_{max})}$	Low rise: $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ s Mid-rise: (4-5 floors) 10^{-4} s (6-7 floors) $2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ s (8-9 floors) $2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ s

² Explicit recommendations can be found in [4]

³ Values based on the information about typical frequency mean values \pm standard deviation for low and medium-rise structures [32] and structural damping value of 1.27% for mixed concrete + steel buildings according to EUROCODE EN 1991-1-4 Table. F.2. For example, for pure steel buildings necessary recording times will be longer. The synchronization error limit and minimum sampling rate is based on the assumption that follows from the investigation done in [22] that usually, f_{max} is around $6f_{min}$ for the third mode shape of buildings.

			(10-12 floors) $2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ s
4.	Minimums sampling rate	$f_s > 2.4f_{max}$	Low rise: 200Hz Mid-rise: (4-5 floors) 100Hz (6-7 floors) 50Hz (8-9 floors) 50Hz (10-12 floors) 50 Hz
5.	Windowing of the signal	-	Example: 20 data segments with 50% overlap and 40 frequency domain averages
6.	The frequency range for each measurement	-	Usually, Nyquist frequency is 50 or 100Hz
7.	Minimums number of sensors	See in text	Depends on the monitoring aim, but the absolute minimum is four channels (four 1D sensors or two 3D sensors)
8.	Expected vibration levels	Maximum 0.25g; In microtremor-based OMA minimum is $10ng\sqrt{Hz}$ over frequency span of interest	Prior testing on site is advised to obtain expected minimum vibration levels. Near intensive traffic sites considerably higher amplitudes $10ng\sqrt{Hz}$ are expected.
9.			

* - recording time can be reduced based on the maximum correlation time in the response according to methodology set in [4].

Note: Calculated values in Tab. 1. are only indicative for choosing the VBM system and should be calculated based on the actual site situation.

5. Section 5 Modal Parameter Identification

Identification of a structural system's modal properties involves comparing the dynamic qualities of a mathematical model to the system's physical features as determined by experimental observations. Large engineering systems like buildings cannot be artificially excited in a controlled manner. Therefore, Operational Modal Analysis (OMA) methods should be used for modal analysis. The parameters of models that characterize building behaviour are estimated using measurement data from operational responses. The structure to be tested is being excited by some excitation with approximately white noise characteristics. For low buildings, this excitation is usually a ground-borne noise from traffic or microtremors. For medium-rise buildings especially with structural schemes such as a sway frame, sufficient wind excitation could be expected. OMA theory performs sufficiently also under weakly nonstationary signals, but care should be taken that excitation has a wide frequency band.

The bandwidth of the excitation frequency spectrum due to traffic load is very much site-dependent. Nevertheless, frequencies with the highest energy input usually are 7 to 15 Hz. These are typical fundamental frequencies of separate building elements like slabs when they are designed to avoid building vibrations or walls. Therefore, care should be taken that actual global building frequencies have been detected for monitoring and not local vibration of building elements.

Before OMA application signal processing routines are obligatory. The following signal-processing steps should be performed:

- Data quality assessment (identification and removal of clipping, dropouts or spikes);
- Detrending (removal of DC offsets);
- Detection of undesired harmonics in the operating signal;
- Digital data filtering (the same filtering must be applied to all channels of data);
- Down-sampling (decimation).

For the application to low and medium-rise buildings, Enhanced Frequency Domain Decomposition (EFDD) and Stochastic Subspace Identification (SSI) is a more frequently used techniques in practice. EFDD is regarded as a user-friendly and fast processing algorithm providing reliable results for estimating natural frequencies and mode shapes even for closely

spaced modes, including repeated modes. SSI technique deals directly with time-series processing and is a parametric method because a function is fitted directly to the raw times series data. The method is robust and allows modal parameter estimation with a high-frequency resolution. Nevertheless, those and other time domain or frequency domain identification techniques could be used if their performance is checked in pilot tests in the object of interest.

6. Damage detection

Different **damage-sensitive features** based on modal parameters have been defined and tested over the years. The most accurate even in the presence of a few installed sensors and therefore recommended for this application is **natural frequencies** [18]. Since **EOVs** yield changes in natural frequency estimate often of the same order of magnitude as those due to damage reliable data normalization procedures should be implemented.

Main sources of EOVs that should be taken under consideration for low and mid-rise buildings:

1. Temperature variations and/or humidity influence almost all **material properties** (e.g. elastic modulus, yield stress and mass density) and typically result in geometric distortion of the structure from some nominal condition. Structures exhibit daily and seasonal temperature variations;
2. Changes in the structure's surroundings or **boundary conditions** such as thermal expansion or fluctuations of ground water near supports [19] can produce significant changes in dynamic responses.

Due to the nonlinear relationship with the mechanical properties of materials and the boundary conditions **output – only data normalization** algorithms are suggested. In this case training data in the healthy condition of the structure should include measurements under a wide range of environmental or operational conditions [20] which is normally full calendar year.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) [21] is currently a well-established and practical output-only method for the effective compensation of EOV effects. Given a multivariate dataset, the standard PCA makes a linear projection of the data aimed at expressing the

covariance structure of the original set of variables as a linear combination of the variables themselves [18].

The ratio between the **fundamental frequency for the fixed base model** of the building and **the elastic spring foundation model** f_{st}/f is the decisive parameter for selecting the building part to be monitored. In the case of a stiff medium-rise building on weak ground, this ratio could be even more than three [22]. Then changes in natural frequencies might be useful for detecting sudden changes in the geological situation under the building base. An application example could be the early detection of hazards in the zones with a risk of karst formation or risks to uneven settlements that cause building cracking or reduction of support area for horizontal elements (e.g. slabs, beams). As for medium-height buildings such as cellular or frame buildings with masonry infills, the most sensitive modal component is found to be the rocking frequency f_r . Thus, if the modal updating is intended, the correct updating of the boundary conditions of the supports should receive the most attention.

Annex

In addition to the recommendations made in these guidelines, it is also possible to find them in guidelines for more general cases or for other specific structures. In [23] are summarized the latest developments of guidelines on the application of SHM techniques, and those are:

- the research network ISIS of Canada presented the “Guidelines for Structural Health Monitoring” in 2001 provides an excellent introduction to SHM techniques to the practising engineer and the manager of infrastructure [24];
- The International Federation for Structural Concrete published the “Monitoring and Safety Evaluation of Existing Concrete Structures” State-of-the-Art Report in 2002 [25] that focusing on bridges;
- The report 'Development of a Model Health Monitoring Guide for Major Bridges' [26] directly addresses bridge health monitoring, condition assessment and operational management;
- ISO presented the ‘Mechanical vibration-Evaluation of measurement results from dynamic tests and investigations on bridges’ (ISO 18649:2004)
- The Europe thematic network SAMCO (Structural Assessment, Monitoring and Control) reported the ‘Guideline for Structural Health Monitoring’ in 2006 [27] compiled by the Federal Institute of Materials Research and Testing (BAM) in Germany;
- ‘Guideline for the Assessment of Existing Structures’ [28] was presented by BAM of SAMCO.

More recently developed guidelines are summarized in [29] and [30]:

- “Technical Specifications of Structural Health Monitoring for Highway Bridges” is a new Chinese structural health monitoring code;
- Technical code (GB 50982-2014) for structural health monitoring of buildings and bridges (no English version);
- GOSTR 53778-2011 introduces the visual inspection, testing technologies and condition-based classification schemes for different types of structures [31].

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